

Effect of Y_2O_3 on the sintering behavior of sol-gel derived zirconia-mullite precursor through inorganic route

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Precursor material for compiling zirconia-mullite composite of higher purity has been synthesized through inorganic route applying co-precipitation and gelation techniques. Pressure-less sintering of the compacted mass has yielded product of dense microstructure with generation of tetragonal zirconia dispersed both in the inter- and intragranular position of mullite matrix.

Various methods for powder processing of a multi-component system have been developed which include co-precipitation, hydrolysis either through aqueous or non-aqueous route. This normally produces high purity, ultrafine powders for the sintered ceramics having fine grained and low porosity structure. With the increase in the requirements for high performance ceramics specially of multi-component system with controlled micro- and macrostructure, attention is being paid towards improvement in the powder preparation and processing as well as fabrication. Among the various composites ZrO_2 -mullite have gained importance due to excellent high temperature strength, chemical inertness, low thermal conductivity and low coefficient of thermal expansion.

There are various methods for preparing zirconia-mullite composites¹. Recent development in the gel technology allows a greater flexibility in incorporation of metastable ZrO_2 particles in mullite matrix². This has been done by the interaction of $Al(NO_3)_3$, $ZrOCl_2$ and tetraethoxysilane in non-aqueous medium. A new fabrication technique for surface infiltration of zirconia into mullite body was carried out. Pre-fired mullite bodies with 20–40% open porosity were infiltrated with a $ZrOCl_2$ solution prior to firing. The mechanical properties of this surface modified mullite improved³. Preparation and mechanical properties of sintered composites were studied⁴.

Present investigation was carried out to synthesize a precursor of ZrO_2 - Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 at a particular mole ratio and subsequent densification of the compacted mass.

Results and Discussion

The gel formation took place from a homogeneous mix-

ture. The dried gel was not very hard which helped in milling. The molar ratio of the individual oxides in the dried gel, as determined by chemical analysis, did not show any significant difference from the batch composition indicating thereby completion of the reaction. The $Al_2O_3 : SiO_2$ molar ratio was found to be identical with traditional mullite composition (Table 1). The batch composition was varied according to the mole % of Y_2O_3 added (Table 2).

Thermal analysis of the mixed hydro-gel represented the nature of expulsion of both loosely and strongly bounded water from the gel meshwork. The first peak at 100° was associated with either the removal of gel water attached with the van der Waals force or by the evaporation of free water from capillary species. Second peak at 160° indicated the dehydration relating to the conversion of polysilicic acid to silica and the third peak at 280° was due to the dehydroxylation of zirconium and aluminium hydroxide⁵. The surface area of the milled powder was sufficiently high (Table 1), which might help the sintering process. This high surface area was also an indication of less agglomeration of particles.

Table 1. Physicochemical characteristics of the prepared hydrogel

Property	
Empirical formula	1.75 ZrO_2 . SiO_2 . 1.5 Al_2O_3
DTGA peak temp. ($^\circ C$)	100, 160, 280
Surface area of the powder (m^2/g)	195
Bulk density (g/cc)	0.824

Before fabrication, the precursor powder was calcined at 950° in order to remove the loosely bound gel water. No extra binder was used. Only 5% uncalcined powder was added. Sintering was operated under normal atmosphere

Table 2. Flexural strength of the samples fired at 1600° under ambient condition

Batch no.	Mole % Y ₂ O ₃ added	Flexural strength MPa
I	0	95
II	3	100
III	6	150
IV	9	128

and the soaking period was kept constant for 2 h. The sintered products were analyzed. The primary effect of heat treatment of precursor powder derived from hydro-gel was manifested in shrinkage caused by removal of residual water followed by material transport during shrinkage. It is to be noted here that the precursor powder was completely amorphous in nature as detected through XRD analysis. The magnitude of shrinkage increased continuously with temperature up to 1600°, the rate being comparatively high up to 1550° (Fig. 1). That the sintering of the precursor powder was promoted by Y₂O₃ was evident from the magnitude of the shrinkage.

Fig. 1. Volume shrinkage vs temperature curves of samples fired at different temperatures.

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e porosity of the green compact was found to be 45.20%, which was sufficiently high. On increasing the temperature of sintering, porosity gradually decreased in all the batch compositions. Significant reduction of porosity was achieved with all the compositions sintered at 1600° among which, the maximum densification was achieved with 3 mole % Y₂O₃ (Batch-II). The change of bulk and true densities indicated that the densification rate increased from 1550° irrespective of batch composition and was manifested by a sharp inflexion point. At 1600° densification was maximum with Batch-II as exhibited in the bulk density curve. This was also in good agreement with the porosity figures.

Mechanical strength of ZrO₂-mullite was found to be strongly influenced by the existence of t-ZrO₂ in the composite. As quantitative measurement of t-ZrO₂ was not carried out and no conclusive statement regarding relationship with t-ZrO₂ could be drawn.

X-Ray diffraction (CuK_α radiation) patterns of the samples sintered at 1550° indicated that mullite formation was positive in all the sample either in presence or absence of Y₂O₃. Moreover, from an analysis of the peak height of mullite phases, it was evident that the content was not significantly affected by the dopant. Y₂O₃ forms solid solution with ZrO₂ to stabilize ZrO₂ in the high temperature form. Thus there was retention of t-ZrO₂ in the mullite matrix during the sintering process. t-ZrO₂ was found to be related to the dopant concentration as revealed from the XRD pattern.

The fracture surface of zirconia mullite composite sintered at 1550° with varying Y₂O₃ dopant was analyzed through SEM analysis (Figs. not shown). The microstructure of zirconia mullite composite without additive is characterized by cross-linked structure of mullite grains along with subrounded to rounded mullite grains. As zirconium has higher atomic number than aluminium and silicon, the zirconium grains differed clearly from the surrounding mullite matrix under SEM observation in showing a brighter image. With the addition of Y₂O₃, the grain boundary became sharper. Zirconia grains were situated mostly in the inter-granular position but in presence of Y₂O₃ some intra-granular zirconia grains were also observed. Inter-granular grains grew probably through grain boundary mass transport of zirconium atom whereas intra-granular grain growth might have taken place by solid solution diffusion of zirconium atom through mullite lattice. Average size of zirconia grain was found to be 0.5 μm. Both zirconia and mullite grain size increased with increasing Y₂O₃ content and with 3 and 9 mole % Y₂O₃ the average grain size was found to be 1.03 μ and 1.55 μ respectively compared to 0.51 μ without any addition. Similarly, the average grain size of mullite increased from 1.28 μ (without addition) to 4.00 μ (with 9 mole % Y₂O₃). Again with the increase in Y₂O₃ content the relative proportion of t-ZrO₂ increased and thus the samples containing higher amounts of Y₂O₃ would be more resistant to transformation.

Experimental

Synthesis of the co-precipitated hydrogel: This was carried out by following the wet interaction technique taking the ingredients in aqueous solution followed by gelation causing destabilization of the sol in presence of a base. The ingredients were Al(NO₃)₃ and ZrOCl₂ salts (AnalaR). Silicic acid was generated by passing sodium silicate solution through a column packed with cation exchanger in H-form. The ingredient solutions were mixed in requisite quantity in a polythene vessel and diluted with deionized water to an overall concentration of 5% (w/v). It was stirred

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thoroughly and then 1 : 1 NH_3 solution was slowly added until the pH reached 9 and the mixture was set to *en bloc* gel. It was allowed to age for 24 h and then filtered and washed with hot de-ionized water till free from soluble impurities. The filtered cake was slowly dried at 60° . Finally it was milled to fine state of subdivision. Table 1 shows properties of the gel.

Y_2O_3 was added in the requisite proportion to the gel powder first by solid state mixing followed by dispersion in acetone medium shaking thoroughly and finally evaporating the solvent. The batch composition was varied according to the mole percent of Y_2O_3 added as detailed in Table 2. Precursor powder containing different mole % Y_2O_3 were consolidated in the form of discs and bars by uniaxial pressing in a hydraulic press.

Conclusion : Noncrystalline active precursor for zirconia-mullite precursor having high surface area was synthesized through coprecipitation and subsequent gelation in aqueous solution. Pressureless sintering of the intimately mixed precursor generated desirable $t-ZrO_2$ and mullite in

presence of Y_2O_3 as dopant. The microstructure consisted of densely packed mullite grains along with mostly intergranular and some intragranular ZrO_2 . The dopant reacted in stabilization of the latter phase.

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